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ZeroW project summary

ZeroW aims to demonstrate significant reduction of Food Loss and Waste (FLW). By the end of the project, our target is to achieve 25% FLW on micro level, through the innovations developed and applied in our 9 Systemic Innovations Living Labs (SILLs). We apply systemic approach for delivering and evaluating all of the project innovations. They are targeted to:

- farmers: wasteless greenhouse solutions for pre-harvest and harvest stages; mobile food processing unit to valorise over-production
- processing: ugly food early identification, shelf-life assessment & alternative valorisation; data-driven poultry production process control & optimisation
- packaging: biodegradable packaging and intelligent label informing retailers of remaining shelf life
- retailers: store/warehouse food waste valorisation, and
- consumers: informing & nudging consumers to make sustainable food choices to reduce household food waste and at the same time keep the high nutritional value of their diet.

ZeroW pays attention to improving the efficiency of the food-bank networks and to the issue of availability and quality of the food supply chain FLW data, based on which companies, local authorities, countries and EC could make effective decisions to reduce the FLW.

The SILLs are the pivot around which we build the rest of the project's important activities: 0FLW dataspace, data-driven solutions for FLW reduction; business exploitation strategies for the innovations. The data gathered through the SILLs, their sustainability assessments and the macro-economic model developed in the project will contribute to policy recommendations for a just transition pathway to near-zero FLW by 2050 and regional scaling-up strategies for FLW reduction innovations. ■